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Experimental Investigation and Optimization of Wet Sliding Wear Behaviour of Biodegradable Mg-1Sn-HA Composites for Orthopaedic Implant Applications using Box-Behnken Design

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Abstract

Objectives: To investigate and optimize the tribological behaviour of Mg-1Sn-xHA biodegradable composites for orthopaedic implant applications. **Methods:** Mg-1Sn-xHA (3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.%) composites were fabricated using stir-assisted squeeze casting. Tribological behaviour was evaluated using a pin-on-disc tribometer under wet sliding conditions. Response Surface Methodology with Box-Behnken design was employed to analyse the effects of reinforcement percentage, rotational speed, axial load, and sliding time on coefficient of friction and frictional force. Statistical analysis using ANOVA was performed to determine parameter significance and optimize tribological performance. **Findings:** It is evident from studies that magnesium composites tribological performance is substantially influenced by hydroxyapatite reinforcement. Mg-1Sn-9HA illustrated the most excellent wear behaviour among the material compositions that were tested, with the lowest coefficient of friction (0.692) and frictional force (13.922 N). With a determination coefficient of over 98%, the significance of the derived models was confirmed by ANOVA, shows a high level of predictive accuracy. Mg-1Sn-9HA composites indicate less abrasive wear due to the stable tribolayer formation and uniform HA dispersion during surface morphology analysis by using pin on disc wear test. On the other hand, reinforcement of the composite (12%HA) results in severe abrasive wear brittle fracture, and particle agglomeration. Optimal tribological conditions were determined by multi-objective optimization to be for about 9.5 wt.% HA reinforcement with a 229 RPM rotational speed, 29.7 N axial load, and 5 minutes sliding time. This research indicates that the controlled hydroxyapatite reinforcement of Mg-1Sn-9HA substantially enhances wear resistance and friction stability, rendering it an effective biodegradable material for

orthopaedic implant applications. The tribological efficacy of biodegradable orthopaedic implants was enhanced through the optimization of Mg–Sn–HA composites using RSM. **Novelty:** This study presents novel technique for fabricating Mg–Sn–HA composites and using statistical optimization (RSM) to determine a most optimal reinforcement level (9 wt.% HA).

Keywords: Mg–Sn alloy; HA reinforcement; Box–Behnken design; RSM; Wet sliding wear optimization; Bio implant applications

1 Introduction

Orthopaedic implants, especially bone plates, metal screws, and fixation devices, are often used to enhance the healing process and stabilize fractured bones in trauma and surgical repair. Stainless steel, chrome–cobalt alloys, and titanium alloys in particular have been used extensively as conventional implant materials due to their exceptional mechanical characteristics and corrosion resistance. However, these materials have a considerably greater modulus of elasticity than normal bone, which frequently results in delaying bone regeneration, bone resorption, and stress shielding. The secondary surgical removal of these irreversible metallic implants after healing is necessary in numerous instances, which results in an increase in medical expenses and the exposure of individuals to wider range of surgical risks, like infection and tissue injury^{(1), (2)}.

Possible alternative methods for orthopaedic implant implantation have emerged in recent years: biodegradable metallic materials. In particular, magnesium (Mg) and their alloys have attracted significant attention for their exceptional mechanical and bio-compatibility in real bone. The Magnesium modulus of elasticity (41–45 GPa) and density (1.74–2.0 g/cm³) are comparable with compact bone, that substantially diminishes the stress shielding effects at the healing duration. Moreover, magnesium ions (Mg²⁺) are essential for human processes of metabolism and bone development, rendering magnesium-based materials highly desirable for biomedical applications^{(3), (4), (5)}.

Though magnesium alloys have several advantages, their fast corrosion rate limits their practical usage in physiological conditions. As a result of the fast degradation of magnesium in fluids from the body, mechanical characteristics of magnesium quickly degrade, and hydrogen gas is produced. These effects might potentially harm the surrounding tissues and reduce the effectiveness of implants. Therefore, improving magnesium alloys tribological behaviour and corrosion resistance is a crucial issue for biomedical applications⁽⁶⁾.

Many approaches have been explored to overcome these limitations, including modification of the surface, alloying, and biodegradable ceramic particle reinforcement. The strength of the material and morphological stability of magnesium can reportedly be enhanced by alloying it with biocompatible elements like tin (Sn), leading to the development of Mg₂Sn intermetallic phases. The presence of these phases in magnesium alloys helps to improve their load-bearing capacity and refine the grain structure. However, galvanic corrosion can occur with an excess of Sn concentration, therefore optimizing the alloy composition with extra caution is required⁽⁷⁾.

Human bone mostly consists of hydroxyapatite (HA), a calcium-based phosphate substance with the molecular formula Ca₁₀(PO₄)(OH)₂. Another potential approach to magnesium reinforcement is calcium carbonate. Hydroxyapatite has several uses in biomedicine because of its chemical similarity to genuine bone tissue, its osteoconductivity, and its remarkable biological function. In supporting enhanced bone-implant integration in magnesium matrix materials, HA particles have been shown to increase mechanical performance, biological stability, corrosion resistance, and the number of favourable implantations^{(8), (9)}.

While the majority of research has concentrated on the mechanical properties and corrosion behaviour of Mg–HA composite materials for biomedical applications, numerous studies have examined this material. Hybrid magnesium composites tribological properties and wear behaviour in simulated physiological conditions are comparatively not explored, particularly in systems that contain both bioactive reinforcements and alloying elements. Furthermore, there is a scarcity of research that has implemented statistical optimization methodologies to assess the combined impact of operating parameters and material composition on tribological responses.

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is an effective statistical tool that enables systematic analysis of multiple variables and their interactions with reduced experimental effort. Among the available experimental designs, the Box–Behnken design (BBD) is widely used for optimization of engineering processes because it efficiently evaluates second-order interactions between process variables⁽¹⁰⁾.

The unique aspect of this research is the use of Response Surface Methodology (RSM), hydroxyapatite (HA) reinforcement and Sn alloying for developing a predictive model for enhanced tribological optimization. In addition to a few positive aspects of this method, it makes it easier to find the optimal reinforcement levels, evaluate parameter interactions precisely and build highly predictive regression models. The proposed approach improves upon previous research by providing a more thorough

and practical knowledge of wear behaviours and friction behaviour under realistic simulated working conditions, this insight is then applied to orthopaedic implant applications.

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the tribological behaviour of Mg–1Sn–xHA ($x = 3, 6, 9,$ and 12 wt.%) hybrid composites fabricated using stir-assisted squeeze casting. The influence of reinforcement percentage, rotational speed, axial load, and sliding time on the coefficient of friction and frictional force is analysed using Response Surface Methodology based on the Box–Behnken design. The study also focuses on identifying the optimal composition and operating conditions for improved tribological performance, thereby developing a biodegradable magnesium composite suitable for load-bearing orthopaedic implant applications.

2 Methodology

2.1 Material Selection

Due to a relatively low density, exceptional biocompatibility and elastic modulus that is comparable to that of native bone, magnesium (Mg) was selected as the matrix material. Through the process of the generation of Mg_2Sn intermetallic phases, tin (Sn) was introduced as an alloying material to enhance the durability and the microstructural consistency of the magnesium matrix. Previous research studies have shown that small amounts of tin can improve mechanical characteristics and grain refinement without significantly altering corrosion behaviour⁽¹¹⁾.

Due to its exceptional biochemical properties, osteoconductivity, and chemical resemblance to the mineral component of natural bone, hydroxyapatite (HA), a calcium phosphate material with the chemical formula $Ca_{10}(PO_4)(OH)_2$, was chosen as the reinforcement phase. The integration of HA particles within magnesium matrices enhances corrosion resistance and facilitates the integration of bone and implant in biomedical uses^{(12), (13)}.

The current investigation developed Mg–1Sn–xHA composites with varying levels of hydroxyapatite reinforcement (3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.%). The tribological behaviour and mechanical durability of the composites that were developed were systematically evaluated in relation to the reinforcement percentage due to the variation in content of HA.

Table 1. The matrix alloy and a reinforcement materials physical and chemical properties

Material	Melting Point (°C)	Density (g/cm ³)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Chemical Composition
Magnesium (Mg)	650	1.74	95–200	40–50	Mg (99.9%)
Tin (Sn)	231.9	7.3	30–50	45–55	Sn (99.9%)
Hydroxyapatite (HA)	>1000	3.16	300–900	80–110	$Ca_{10}(PO_4)(OH)_2$

Magnesium is an appropriate material for load-supporting biomedical implants due to its near-human cortical bone-like density and elastic modulus, as illustrated in Table 1. Hydroxyapatite reinforcement further improves the mechanical compatibility and bioactivity of the composite material.

2.2 Composite Fabrication

The Mg–1Sn–xHA composites were made using stir-assisted squeeze casting, a typical process of fabricating metal matrix composites with uniform reinforcement distribution and improved mechanical characteristics. This technique reduces development of porosity during solidification while allowing the efficient variation of ceramic particles inside the molten metal⁽¹⁴⁾.

Initially, the magnesium and the tin were reconstituted in a crucible of graphite within an electric resistant furnace at temperatures ranging from around 650–680°C. The heated hydroxyapatite material particles were progressively incorporated into the melting process to avoid the risk of thermal shock and particle aggregation once the molten material reached a semi-liquid state.

A graphite-coated stirrer was employed to perform mechanical agitating at a rotational speed of 500–600 rpm approximately 8–10 minutes in order to produce a uniform dispersal of HA particles in the magnesium matrix. After sufficient mixing, the molten composite slurry was transferred into a preheated steel die under applied pressure to form cylindrical billets. The overall fabrication process of Mg–1Sn–xHA composites is illustrated in Figure 1.

The squeeze casting technique improves particle–matrix bonding and reduces casting defects such as porosity, thereby enhancing the structural integrity of the developed composites⁽¹⁵⁾.

Fig 1. Schematic representation of stir-assisted squeeze casting used for fabrication of Mg–1Sn–xHA hybrid composites

2.3 Wear Testing Procedure

Tribological experiments were conducted using a pin-on-disc tribometer under wet sliding conditions in accordance with the ASTM G99 standard. This test method is commonly used to evaluate the friction and wear behaviour of metallic biomaterials under controlled conditions⁽¹⁶⁾.

Cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 10 mm and length of 30 mm were machined from the fabricated composite billets and used as pin samples. The counterface material consisted of a hardened EN31 steel disc with hardness of 62 HRC and track diameter of 100 mm.

To ensure reliable surface conditions and eliminate contaminants, the areas of contact of the formal specimens were polished with emery paper of different grain sizes and cleansed with acetone prior to testing. The coefficient of friction and frictional force was constantly recorded as the composite pin was repeatedly struck with the rotating disc under a predetermined axial load during the testing process. The experimental configuration with the pin-on-disc tribometer employed in this investigation is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig 2. A pin-on-disc tribometer for tribological properties of Mg–1Sn–xHA composites

Two response parameters were used to evaluate the tribological behaviour: Frictional force (FF) and coefficient of friction (COF) These reactions provide insight into the proposed composites contact stabilization and wear resistance under simulated sliding experimental conditions⁽¹⁷⁾.

2.4 Experimental Design Using Response Surface Methodology

A systematic evaluation of the influence of process factors on tribological behaviour was conducted using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) with the Box-Behnken design (BBD). Formal engineering studies often use RSM, a statistical optimization method, to evaluate the interaction of several factors and develop numerical models for prediction⁽¹⁸⁾.

Four parameters were selected for conducting the experimental studies

- Reinforcement percentage (A)
- Rotational speed (B)
- Axial load (C)
- Sliding time (D)

Each factor was evaluated at three levels low (-1), medium (0) and high (+1). The input parameters have been chosen, and their respective levels are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Input factor and their levels – BBD

Input Factor	Unit	Low (-1)	Medium (0)	High (+1)
Reinforcement	%	6	9	12
Rotational Speed	RPM	200	400	600
Axial Load	N	10	20	30
Sliding Time	min	5	10	15

The Box-Behnken design created 29 experimental trials, which allowed for effective assessment of parameter interactions and reduced the number of experiments that were necessary. The experimental responses obtained from these trials were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to assess the statistically significant influence of each factor.

Subsequently, a second-order polynomial regressive model was created to determine a mathematical relationship between the values of the input parameters and the output response. It is standard procedure to use such predictive models to improve the tribological performance of metal matrix composites⁽¹⁹⁾.

2.5 Optimization Using Desirability Function

For an evaluation of the optimal operating conditions for improved tribological performance using the desirability function technique, a multifunctional optimization strategy was used. The goal of the optimization was to simultaneously decrease the coefficient of friction and the frictional force.

The desirability function takes into account a number of responses and produces a composite desirability index that is unique and can take values between 0 and 1, indicating an ideal situation. A combination of input parameters that result in the ideal expected behaviour level is an optimal condition for achieving the tribological effectiveness displayed by the composite material⁽²⁰⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Experimental Design and Response Analysis

The BBD from Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was used to evaluate the tribological performance of the fabricated Mg-1Sn-xHA composites. In order to create 29 experimental combinations, the experimental design varied the rotational speed, axial load, reinforcement percentage, and sliding time at three distinct levels. Table 3 shows the responses derived for the coefficient of friction (COF) and frictional force (FF).

According to the findings in Table 3, the tribological behaviour of Mg-Sn-HA composites is substantially influenced by both the reinforcement percentage and the operating parameters. The coefficient of friction generally decreased as the hydroxyapatite content increased, and this phenomenon can be associated to the creation of a stabilized tribolayer at a sliding interface, up to a certain threshold. In contrast, the friction behaviour was adversely affected by the agglomeration of particles and the resulting a greater surface roughness, which were the consequences of the excessive HA content.

Table 3. Experimental design matrix and relevant tribological responses

Std	Reinforcement	Rotational Speed	Axial Load	Sliding Time	COF	FF
	%	RPM	N	Minutes	-	N
1	6	200	20	10	0.821	17.245
2	12	200	20	10	0.705	14.752
3	6	400	20	10	0.748	16.485
4	12	400	20	10	0.812	16.647
5	9	300	10	5	0.752	15.352
6	9	300	30	5	0.699	14.568
7	9	300	10	15	0.703	15.352
8	9	300	30	15	0.698	16.532
9	6	300	20	5	0.778	16.475
10	12	300	20	5	0.728	14.952
11	6	300	20	15	0.732	17.025
12	12	300	20	15	0.725	16.082
13	9	200	10	10	0.735	15.555
14	9	400	10	10	0.778	15.885
15	9	200	30	10	0.732	15.228
16	9	400	30	10	0.745	15.752
17	6	300	10	10	0.735	17.098
18	12	300	10	10	0.725	14.568
19	6	300	30	10	0.725	15.947
20	12	300	30	10	0.703	15.652
21	9	200	20	5	0.755	15.025
22	9	400	20	5	0.789	15.456
23	9	200	20	15	0.735	16.139
24	9	400	20	15	0.766	16.895
25	9	300	20	10	0.785	17.085
26	9	300	20	10	0.787	17.125
27	9	300	20	10	0.795	17.061
28	9	300	20	10	0.792	17.125
29	9	300	20	10	0.799	17.452

3.2 ANOVA Analysis for Coefficient of Friction

A Statistical Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to assess the regression model's statistical significance. Table 4 summarizes the coefficient of friction data.

Based on the ANOVA results, the model that was developed is statistically significant, with an F-value of 75.27 and a p-value that is less than 0.0001. Excellent agreement between experimental and predicted results is indicated by the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 98.69\%$). The tribological behaviour of metallic matrix composites has been accurately predicted by RSM models in recent studies, which have reported similar findings.

3.3 Frictional Force Analysis

The frictional force values acquired from the experiments were also analyzed using ANOVA to evaluate the significance of process parameters. Table 5 represents the point at which the ANOVA results for frictional force are presented.

The statistical results indicate that the frictional force is most significantly influenced by the reinforcement percentage, followed by the sliding time and rotational speed. In comparison to other parameters, axial load demonstrated a statistically significant reduced level of significance. The regression model's reliability was confirmed by its high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 98.46\%$).

Table 4. Presents the coefficient of friction ANOVA findings

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	0.036	14	0.0026	75.27	< 0.0001	Significant
A-Reinforcement	0.0017	1	0.0017	48.51	< 0.0001	
B-Rotational Speed	0.002	1	0.002	58.62	< 0.0001	
C-Axial Load	0.0013	1	0.0013	38.74	< 0.0001	
D-Sliding Time	0.0017	1	0.0017	49.2	< 0.0001	
AB	0.0081	1	0.0081	237.18	< 0.0001	
AC	0	1	0	1.05	0.322	
AD	0.0005	1	0.0005	13.54	0.0025	
BC	0.0002	1	0.0002	6.59	0.0224	
BD	2.25E-06	1	2.25E-06	0.0659	0.8012	
CD	0.0006	1	0.0006	16.87	0.0011	
A²	0.003	1	0.003	86.51	< 0.0001	
B²	0	1	0	0.5223	0.4817	
C²	0.0145	1	0.0145	423.44	< 0.0001	
D²	0.0062	1	0.0062	182.13	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.0005	14	0			Not Significant
Lack of Fit	0.0003	10	0	1.06	0.5229	
Pure Error	0.0001	4	0			
Cor Total	0.0365	28				

Table 5. Displays the outcomes of the ANOVA for frictional force

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	22.01	14	1.57	63.89	< 0.0001	significant
A-Reinforcement	4.84	1	4.84	196.73	< 0.0001	
B-Rotational Speed	0.8406	1	0.8406	34.16	< 0.0001	
C-Axial Load	0.0014	1	0.0014	0.0581	0.813	
D-Sliding Time	3.2	1	3.2	130.05	< 0.0001	
AB	1.76	1	1.76	71.61	< 0.0001	
AC	1.25	1	1.25	50.75	< 0.0001	
AD	0.0841	1	0.0841	3.42	0.0857	
BC	0.0094	1	0.0094	0.3824	0.5463	
BD	2.64E-02	1	2.64E-02	1.07	0.3178	
CD	0.9643	1	0.9643	39.19	< 0.0001	
A ²	0.7061	1	0.7061	28.69	0.0001	
B ²	2.06	1	2.06	83.53	< 0.0001	
C ²	6.61	1	6.61	268.78	< 0.0001	
D ²	3.31	1	3.31	134.49	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.3445	14	0.0246			Not significant
Lack of Fit	0.2418	10	0.0242	0.9421	0.5756	
Pure Error	0.1027	4	0.0257			
Cor Total	22.36	28				

3.4 Importance of Process Parameters on Frictional Force and Coefficient of Friction

The coefficient of friction (COF) and frictional force (FF) of Mg–1Sn–xHA composites are influenced by the combined effects of rotational speed, axial load, sliding time, and reinforcement percentage, as demonstrated by the response surface plots in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The tribological behaviour of the composites that have been developed is clearly illustrated by the effect of interaction involving the process parameters in these figures.

The coefficient of friction reduces as the hydroxyapatite reinforcement is raised from 6 wt.% to approximately 9 wt.%, as depicted in Figure 3. This phenomenon can be attributed to the development of a stable tribolayer at the sliding surface and enhanced hardness. In contrast, a slight increase in COF is observed as a consequence of particle agglomeration and enhanced surface roughness when the reinforcement content is further increased to 12 wt.%. Figure 4. illustrates comparable trend in terms of frictional force, as moderate reinforcement levels exhibit improved load-bearing capacity and decreased frictional resistance.

The friction behaviour is also substantially influenced by rotational speed, as evidenced by the interaction plots. Increasing the rotational speed generally reduces both COF and frictional force due to reduced contact time between the sliding surfaces and improved formation of lubricating oxide layers. Conversely, increasing the axial load leads to higher COF and frictional force as the real contact area between the pin and disc surfaces increases.

Furthermore, sliding time shows a gradual influence on friction behaviour. Initially, friction increases as the surfaces adapt to contact conditions, but prolonged sliding may lead to stabilization of friction due to the development of a protective tribolayer. Overall, the interaction analysis presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4. indicates that moderate reinforcement levels (around 9 wt.% HA) under optimized operating conditions result in the lowest coefficient of friction and frictional force, demonstrating the superior tribological performance of the Mg–1Sn–9HA composite.

3.5 Surface Morphology Analysis of Wear

The surface morphology of the worn Mg–1Sn–xHA composites after tribological testing was examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to identify the dominant wear mechanisms under different hydroxyapatite (HA) reinforcement levels. The SEM micrographs presented in Figure 5(a–c) illustrate the worn surface characteristics of the composites containing 6 wt.% HA, 9 wt.% HA, and 12 wt.% HA, respectively.

The SEM micrograph of Mg–1Sn–6HA (Figure 5a) shows prominent ploughing grooves aligned with the sliding direction along with scattered wear debris and localized surface deformation. These characteristics reveal the formation of adhesive and mixed abrasive wear mechanisms. Hardness and bearing weight capacity of the material are only partially improved by the relatively low HA reinforcement, which results in increased deformation of plastic and material loss during sliding contact.

Conversely, the Mg–1Sn–9HA composite (Figure 5b) demonstrates wear observes that are comparatively smoother, with shallow voids and minimal plastic deformation. The surface hardness is improved, and direct metal-to-metal contact is reduced during sliding due to the existence of a steady tribolayer and equally distributed HA particles. This protective layer enhances the tribological rigidity and substantially reduces wear, suggesting that this composite has superior wear resistance.

SEM analysis of Mg–1Sn–12HA particles (Figure 5c) exhibits extensive surface damage, which is defined by deep voids, degradation, HA particle aggregation, and microcracks. The brittle behaviour and particle clustering that result from the excess HA reinforcement accelerate material elimination during sliding and increase the level of stress at the interface.

In general, the SEM observations suggest that the fabricated Mg–1Sn–9HA composite exhibits the most favourable wear behaviour, as evidenced by its stable tribolayer formation and smoother wear tracks. These results are consistent according to the tribological test findings, which demonstrated that the fabricated Mg–1Sn–9HA composite showed a minimal coefficient of friction along with frictional force based on optimized conditions.

3.6 Optimization of Tribological Parameters

A desirability function approach was employed to perform multi-objective optimization in order to ascertain the optimum operating circumstances for a minimal amount of frictional force along with the coefficient of friction. Table 6 provides a summary of the optimization results.

The optimum frictional responses were achieved with an approximate 9.5 wt.% hydroxyapatite reinforced material, which is the optimal condition. These results verify that a Mg–1Sn–9HA composite demonstrates the most well-balanced combination of mechanical performance and tribological stability.

These findings are in line with more recent research that found that reinforcement mg composites increased their tribological performance via strengthening them harder and stimulating the development of tribolayer. There have been reports of hybrid Mg composites with ceramic reinforcements having increased wear resistance, for instance⁽²¹⁾. In a similar vein, the present

Fig 3. Interaction 3D Surface plots for COF

Fig 4. Interaction 3D Surface plots for Friction Force

Fig 5. SEM images of Wear surfaces of (6wt%, 9wt% and 12wt%) HA reinforcement

Table 6. The optimal tribological parameter values for Mg–1Sn–xHA composites

S. No	Reinforcement	Rotational Speed	Axial Load	Sliding Time	COF	FF	Desirability
1	9.518	229.615	29.752	5.011	0.692	13.992	1.000 Selected
2	9.792	294.745	29.907	5.078	0.696	14.383	1.000
3	9.888	305.564	29.971	5.086	0.696	14.404	1.000
4	10.011	243.98	29.967	6.467	0.697	14.545	1.000

research finds that, up to an optimum HA concentration of around 9 wt.%, the coefficient of friction and frictional force are lowered.

This study offers a thorough tribological investigation under different working situations, in contrast to previous studies that primarily concentrate on mechanical and corrosion aspects (22), (23). Also, unlike previous research, these shows that using too much reinforcement (12 wt.% HA) causes particles to clump together and reduces wear performance.

There has been not much of systematic multi-parameter optimization in the literature, despite the fact that recent studies have placed an emphasis on biodegradability and material development (24). This paper provides a more robust and application-oriented method by using Response Surface Methodology (RSM), which allows for accurate prediction and interaction analysis ($R^2 > 98\%$).

This work significantly contributes insights beyond just confirming prior results, it provides perspectives on optimal reinforcement levels as well as tribological behaviour, expanding the scope of its impact.

4 Conclusion

After being successfully fabricated and examined for tribological performance, Mg–1Sn–xHA hybrid materials with hydroxyapatite (HA) reinforcing levels of 3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.% were produced using stir-assisted pressurized casting. Utilizing the Box–Behnken experimental design, the Response Surface Methodology was deployed to investigate the impact of reinforcement percentage, rotational speeds, axial load and sliding time on COF and FF.

According to experiments, magnesium alloy tribology is significantly influenced by hydroxyapatite reinforcement. The optimum performance was best for the Mg–1Sn–9HA composite, which exhibited the least coefficient of friction and frictional force. The magnesium matrix's uniform dispersion of HA particles enhances surface hardness and facilitates the formation of a strong protecting tribolayer during sliding.

Significant and reliable regression models were demonstrated by the ANOVA. A significant level of accord between the prediction and the experiment is indicated by coefficient of the determination values at or above 98%. Rotational speed and reinforcement percentage were the most vital parameters in the process for friction behaviour.

Analysis of the surface morphology using scanning electron microscopy showed that different wear processes were seen depending on the quantity of reinforcement. Friction wear, aggregation of particles, delamination of the material, and brittle fracture were prominent features of the Mg-1Sn-12HA composite, in contrast to the superficial cracks and negligible surface damage observed in the Mg-1Sn-9HA composite.

Mult objective optimization, which makes use of the desirability function, determined that a desirable tribological conditions are as follows: 9.5 wt.% HA reinforcement, 229 RPM rotating speed, 29.7 N axial load, and 5 minutes sliding time. A minimum frictional force of 13.992 N and coefficient of friction of 0.692 were the results of this process.

Biodegradable orthopaedic implant applications such as bone plates, fixation fasteners, and spinal cages are being considered for the Mg-1Sn-9HA hybrid composite because of its optimum combination of tribological stability, mechanical strength, and biological compatibility. The clinical potential of the improved composite should be confirmed by conducting tests for biodegradation, over time corrosion, and in-vitro biocompatibility.

Novelty and Key Contributions of the Study:

The tribology of biomaterials used in orthopaedic implants that contain magnesium was improved by creating Mg-1Sn-xHA hybrid biodegradable composites via stir-assisted squeeze casting. By methodically evaluating operating parameters and reinforcing %, RSM (Response Surface Methodology) with a Box-Behnken design was employed to analyze and optimize friction behaviour. The optimal combination was Mg-1Sn-9HA because its consistent tribolayer development and homogenous HA dispersion reduced wear and friction. To minimize frictional force and coefficient of friction, the optimal tribological conditions were determined using statistical optimization. These new findings show the way for orthopaedic implants that carry weight and are biodegradable, as well as composites of magnesium that are more resistant to corrosion.

Future Work Scope:

Researchers should look at the biodegradation and corrosion of the upgraded Mg-1Sn-9HA composite in artificial body fluids in future studies. Its biological stability for orthopaedic usage must be confirmed by in-vitro cell cytocompatibility and bioactivity investigations. Researchers may look for ways to improve corrosion resistance and degradation by surface modification and microscopic structure improvement in future studies. Tests of biodegradable composite implants mechanical stability and in vivo testing are necessary for their future application.

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About authors: SG is a Registered Research Scholar under Annamalai University and also serves as an Assistant Professor in Sri Sai Ram Engineering College; SR serves as Professor in Annamalai University; AG serves as Associate Professor in Sri Sai Ram Engineering College; SR serves as Professor in Annamalai University; GB serves as Assistant Professor in Arasu Engineering College; VA serves as Assistant Professor in S. S. Polytechnic College.

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